

Polarimetric Estimation of Palladium

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Polarimetric estimation of palladium has been made quite rapidly and with a fair degree of accuracy with a solution of palladium chloride mixed with strychnine acetate solution, resulting in the formation of a yellow-brown precipitate. Weight of Pd (II) is calculated by the use of an empirical equation.

Alkaloids find use as microchemical reagents in qualitative and quantitative analysis of metals. Liteanu and Cosma¹ used quinine monochlorohydrate as a precipitant for polarimetric estimation of Hg(II) in the form of optically active compound formed between quinine and potassium iodomercurate. The angle of rotation of the compound in acetone was measured with the help of a polarimeter and weight of Hg(II) in a given volume of solution was calculated by employing an empirical equation derived on the basis of experimental data. This method has been extended by us in polarimetric estimation of cadmium² and bismuth³. The present communication describes a method for polarimetric estimation of Pd(II) based on similar principles.

Whitmore and Schneider⁴ studied the reactions of brucine, caffeine, cinchonidine, einchophen, cocaine, sparteine, quinidine sulphate, quinine, and strychnine on palladium chloride. Due to high optical rotatory power of brucine, quinine, and strychnine, we studied the reactions of these alkaloids on palladium chloride and concluded that strychnine was most suitable for purposes of polarimetric estimation of Pd (II).

EXPERIMENTAL

Estimations were carried out by using different volumes of palladium chloride solutions, containing 0.3333 g. in 200 ml. Volumes of solutions taken for different estimations were from 2.5 ml to 13 ml, corresponding to 2.43 mg. to 12.61 mg. of Pd(II). To each of these solutions, taken in separate beakers, was added half of the volume of strychnine acetate solution (5 g./250 ml containing a few ml of glacial acetic acid). The contents in the beakers were heated nearly to 80°, left undisturbed for sometime at the room temperature, and finally cooled in ice so as to ensure complete precipitation. Yellow-brown precipitate obtained was filtered, washed with a few ml of light petroleum, and dissolved in 50 ml of dioxane-water-acetone (5:4:1) mixture. This solution was used for polarimetric measurements at the room temperature, using a 2-dcm tube. The least count of the instrument used was 0.01°.

1. *Talanta*, 1961, **8**, 313; *Anal. Abs.*, 1962, **9**, No. 48.
2. Perti and Prakash, *Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci., India*, 1964, **34A**, 1.
3. *Idem*, unpublished.
4. *Mikrochem.*, 1935, **17**, 279.

Variations of angle of rotation with the corresponding change in concentrations of Pd(II) from 2.43 to 12.61 mg./50 ml are shown in Table I. In Table II a comparison is made between polarimetrically estimated values, obtained from the empirical equation (*vide infra*), and gravimetrically estimated values, using dimethylglyoxime as precipitant.

TABLE I

Pd(II) /50ml (mg.)	..	2.43	4.85	7.28	9.70	10.67	12.61
Angle of rotation for Hg _{346r}	..	0.15°	0.28°	0.40°	0.52°	0.57°	0.63°

DISCUSSION

A plot of concentration against optical rotation shows a linear relationship (Fig. 1).

FIG. 1

On the basis of experimental data, the following equation of the curve has been calculated by the method of least squares:

$$W = 20.67R - 0.8612 \text{ Pd(II) mg./50 ml}$$

[where W is the weight of Pd(II) in mg./50 ml and R is the angle of rotation in degree]. The degree of accuracy of this empirical equation has been shown in Table II.

TABLE II

PdCl ₂ soln. taken.	Palladium (II) found		Diff. (a) - (b).
	Gravimetrically (a).	Polarimetrically (b).	
2.5 ml	2.43 mg	2.24 mg.	+0.19 mg.
5.0	4.85	4.93	-0.08
7.5	7.28	7.41	-0.13
10.0	9.70	9.89	-0.19
11.0	10.67	10.92	-0.25
13.0	12.61	12.16	+0.45

Table II shows clearly that polarimetrically estimated weight of Pd(II) provides fairly accurate results from 5 to 12.5 mg. of Pd (II) per 50 ml.

Polarimetric method of estimating Pd (II) is thus fairly accurate and it can well be compared with colorimetric methods of estimations⁵. The method is easier and quicker as compared with colorimetric method and can be applied where rapid and routine estimation of metallic ions [Pd(II)] is required. The method can be made more useful if its sensitivity and accuracy are enhanced by employing an objective apparatus, i.e., photoelectrical method of recording rotations. A further increase in accuracy would be possible by carrying out measurements in ultraviolet where the rotation values would be much higher.

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